

Unravelling the black box between coepetition and firms' sustainability performance

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ABSTRACT

Despite the widely advocated positive impact of coepetition on firms' sustainability performance, there is a lack of research-based explanations for the underlying mechanism linking these two variables. This study investigates the role of dynamic capabilities and sustainability awareness as mediators and necessary conditions for the relationship between coepetition and firms' sustainability performance. Drawing on data from the Norwegian fishing industry, our analysis demonstrates a significant association between coepetition and an increase in dynamic capabilities and sustainability awareness. Additionally, dynamic capabilities and sustainability awareness are significantly related to improved firms' sustainability performance. Importantly, the direct effect of coepetition becomes insignificant when considering the two mediating variables, indicating full mediation by dynamic capabilities and sustainability awareness. Further analysis reveals that these two factors are also necessary conditions for enhancing firms' sustainability performance. Based on these findings, we provide actionable recommendations to guide appropriate managerial and policy interventions.

1. Introduction

Coepetition, which refers to collaboration between firms that are simultaneously involved in both cooperation and competition (Bengtsson & Kock, 2014, p. 182), has recently received attention from both scholars and practitioners as a potential strategy to achieve sustainability (Gnyawali & Song, 2016; Mirzabeiki et al., 2022). While recent studies have extensively examined the relationship between coepetition and firms' economic benefits (e.g. Crick & Crick, 2021; Deng et al., 2021; Fernandez et al., 2021), there is a notable absence of scholarly insights concerning the underlying mechanism linking coepetition to sustainability performance (Mirzabeiki et al., 2022). Although coepetition is widely advocated for its various positive impacts, the lack of a theory regarding its fundamental properties and their influence on outcomes hinders progress in coepetition theory (Gnyawali & Charleton, 2018). Mirzabeiki et al. (2022) support this assertion in the context of sustainability performance, noting that none of the prior studies have successfully elucidated the mechanisms that enable coepetition to deliver desirable sustainable outcomes. Intriguingly, Mirzabeiki et al. (2022) posited that their research identified how coepetition could effectively improve sustainability performance. Specifically, their findings suggest that coepetition can reduce logistics costs and carbon footprints, bolster the competitiveness of the regional economy, and mitigate emissions (Mirzabeiki et al., 2022).

Nevertheless, it is important to note that a mechanism is an

underlying process that explains how a specific variable associated with coepetition influences an outcome (Gnyawali & Charleton, 2018). Thus, we contend that the factors Mirzabeiki et al. (2022) identified do not constitute a mechanism through which coepetition influences sustainability. Instead, these factors represent distinct elements of sustainability performance that coepetition can positively affect. Hence, there remains a lack of research-based explanations regarding how coepetition influences sustainability performance. Such explanations are crucial because elaborating on how coepetition generates certain outcomes is critical for advancing coepetition theory (Gnyawali & Charleton, 2018). Therefore, this study's attempt to unravel the mediating mechanism between coepetition and firms' sustainability performance contributes to the literature on sustainability performance and advances the literature on coepetition.

Before this study, a preliminary qualitative exploration was conducted. This exploration involved conducting semi-structured interviews with actors in the Norwegian fishing industry. We chose the Norwegian fishing industry because its characteristics render it suitable for examining the dynamics of coepetition (Lindland et al., 2019; Sogn-Grundvåg et al., 2021). The study highlighted the pivotal role of coepetition in fostering the development of dynamic capabilities, such as knowledge management, organisational responsiveness, and reflexive control. Additionally, it was revealed that coepetition enhances actors' sustainability awareness, consequently leading to improved sustainability performance. Consistent with the extant literature, this

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qualitative study highlights the importance of dynamic capabilities for sustainability performance in a rapidly changing business environment. For instance, Kumar et al. (2018, p. 99) assert that ‘it is necessary for firms to build dynamic capabilities in a dynamic business environment to achieve sustainable performance’. Similarly, Gold et al. (2010, p. 230) suggested that capabilities evolving from collaboration (e.g. dynamic capabilities) are prerequisites or necessary for implementing sustainable practices, hence improving firm sustainability performance. Such capabilities are viewed as higher-order constructs because they emerge through learning as organisations modify their relatively stable collective routines to fit uncertain environments (Alinaghian et al., 2020; Aslam et al., 2018; Teece, 2014). Although these assertions are appealing, there have been no efforts to verify them empirically.

In addition to dynamic capabilities, firms are encouraged to shift their mindset to enhance sustainable performance (Crick & Crick, 2021; De Smet, Gao, Henderson and Hundertmark, 2021). In this regard, we argue that the role of sustainability awareness in linking cooptation to sustainability performance is plausible because changing mindsets must involve cultivating and sustaining sustainability awareness within firms. Nonetheless, the existing literature has not empirically explored the effects of cooptation on sustainability awareness and its subsequent impact on sustainability performance. This study advances the literature in three ways. First, we advance cooptation theory by proposing and empirically testing a mechanism that governs the relationship between cooptation and sustainability performance. Second, this is one of the first studies to explore the role of dynamic capabilities and sustainability awareness as necessary conditions for attaining firm sustainability performance using a recently developed method that combines partial least structural equation modelling and necessary condition analysis (Richter et al., 2020). Third, the study offers practical managerial insights relevant to the fishing industry and other industries with similar characteristics. The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature and develops the hypotheses. Section 3 outlines the methods, followed by Section 4, which presents the analysis and results. Section 5 presents the managerial and theoretical implications of the findings. Section 6 summarises the study and identifies limitations and opportunities for further research.

2. Literature review and hypotheses development

As highlighted in the introduction, this study proposes dynamic capabilities and sustainability awareness as mediating mechanisms that link cooptation to sustainability performance. Fig. 1 visually depicts this conceptualisation and illustrates its four hypotheses. The subsequent subsections present the relevant literature and provide arguments to support these hypotheses.

2.1. Cooptation and dynamic capabilities - H1

Dynamic capability theory (DCT) addresses how firms can achieve temporary and long-term competitive advantages in changing business environments (Beske et al., 2014; Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Teece et al., 1997). The theory builds on the critique of the resource-based view and challenges the assumption that a firm's business environment is static and relatively unchanging (Govindan, 2018; Chen & Chang, 2013). Thus, it argues that capabilities that give a firm a competitive advantage can become less valuable or disappear in a rapidly changing environment (Beske, 2012; Govindan, 2018; Teece et al., 1997). One reason is that such environments require constant market assessment and the adoption of best practices and technologies (Mishra et al., 2022; Teece et al., 1997). Hence, dynamic capabilities are critical for achieving and maintaining a competitive advantage. Such capabilities represent ‘the firm's ability to purposefully integrate, build, and reconfigure its resource base to respond to rapidly changing environment’ (Teece et al., 1997, p.516). They are critical because they help firms respond, reconfigure resources, and accomplish strategic goals, such as optimising sustainability goals and firms' overall performance (Beske, 2012; Crick & Crick, 2022; Park et al., 2014).

Dynamic capabilities are essentially higher-order capabilities that emerge from infinite learning, best practices, and renewing collective organisational routines, resources, and assets (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Teece, 2014; Winter, 2003). Notably, Zollo and Winter (2002) emphasise that while dynamic capabilities are considered higher-order capabilities, firms must consistently engage in learning processes to adapt and update them in the face of a rapidly changing environment. Therefore, as firms actively pursue continuous learning, their dynamic capabilities increase, which in turn contributes to sustainable performance (Teece, 2014). However, firms need a good business strategy to

Fig. 1. Conceptual model.

help them deploy scarce resources and facilitate learning to develop effective dynamic capabilities and achieve desired goals (e.g. sustainable performance) (Martin, 2011; Teece et al., 2016). Dyer et al. (2018) argue that it is worthwhile for firms to invest in a collaborative business strategy (e.g. cooptation) that fosters the creation of dynamic capabilities, especially in a rapidly changing environment.

Cooptation manifests when competitors cooperate in some activities and compete in others (Bengtsson & Kock, 2000; Ritala, 2001). Thus, it is a context-dependent strategy based on multiple levels of paradoxical tensions between competition and cooperation (Monticelli et al., 2023). Recent studies (e.g. Crick & Crick, 2022; Dentoni et al., 2016; Mirzabeiki et al., 2022; Song et al., 2016) suggest that cooptation can generate dynamic capabilities. This is because cooptation, like other modes of collaboration, can be a vehicle for organisational learning (Aslam et al., 2020; Teece et al., 1997), helping firms continuously modify their stable collective routines through regular meetings and training (Chauhan et al., 2022; Gold et al., 2010; Siems et al., 2021; Zollo & Winter, 2002). Similarly, Song et al. (2016) argue that cooptation facilitates parallel development and dual sourcing, enabling firms to share knowledge and innovation and develop promising technologies that allow firms to capitalise on changes in a rapidly changing environment. They also highlight that cooptation enables firms to reconfigure their resources and assets by acquiring new relevant knowledge. In summary, cooptation can be essential in developing dynamic capabilities that allow firms to effectively navigate rapidly changing environments (Bouncken et al., 2018; Dentoni et al., 2016; Munten et al., 2021).

Consistent with DCT, we anticipate that actors in the fishing industry can leverage cooptation in several ways. For example, they can allow them to improve their traceability and transparency capabilities through technological diffusion and spread (Seuring et al., 2022; Silva et al., 2021). It can also help develop common standard guidelines and joint control mechanisms that allow them to respond to new changes in a constantly changing environment (Aslam et al., 2018; Beske et al., 2014; Ghadge et al., 2017). Similarly, it can improve firms' ability to change their operations in response to unforeseen events and new opportunities (Crick & Crick, 2022; Geyi et al., 2020; Rajaguru & Matanda, 2019). Accordingly, we argue that cooptation can help fishing industry actors develop dynamic capabilities. Therefore, we propose the following hypothesis:

H1. As firms engage in cooptation, their dynamic capabilities will likely increase.

2.2. Dynamic capabilities and firms' sustainability performance - H2

Consistent with Li (2022), we regard a firm's sustainability performance as entailing economic, social, and environmental optimisation. Therefore, in this context, dynamic capabilities reflect the ability of firms to develop and modify resources and capabilities to achieve favourable economic, social, and environmental outcomes in a rapidly changing environment. The fishing industry is characterised by rapid market changes, making it an excellent example of a dynamic industry (Harun et al., 2022). Rapid changes compel actors to adjust accordingly, such as redesigning organisational processes and reallocating resources (Easterby-Smith et al., 2009; Fredrich et al., 2019; Govindan, 2018). This requires firms to constantly evaluate and adjust their resource bases and collective routines (Dyer et al., 2018; Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Zollo & Winter, 2002). Considering that sustainability practices require technology-based innovations (Mishra et al., 2022) and changes in operations and strategies (Gold et al., 2010; Gruchmann et al., 2019; Siems et al., 2021), and because dynamic capabilities can facilitate such changes, we argue that dynamic capabilities are critical for optimising the three dimensions of sustainability performance. Accordingly, we propose the following hypothesis:

H2. There is a positive association between firms' dynamic capabilities and improvement in their sustainability performance.

2.3. Cooptation and sustainability awareness - H3

In this study, we define sustainability awareness as the degree to which actors understand the concept of sustainability and its relevance. Plausibly, sustainability awareness precedes sustainable practices because for someone to act on something, they must first become aware of it. For instance, to acquire new customers, marketers implement various tactics to raise customer awareness, leading to the desire and purchase of a product. Collaboration is a potential source of sustainability awareness because it is essential for sharing sustainability insights (Gold et al., 2010; Press et al., 2014). Conceivably, sustainability awareness is achieved when sufficient information, experiences, and knowledge are widely shared and integrated among collaborators (Gericke et al., 2019; Sarrica et al., 2016).

Like any other form of collaboration, cooptation serves as a vehicle for promoting awareness as it reduces information uncertainty (Chauhan et al., 2022; Wilhelm, 2011). Sharing knowledge and past experiences or actions through cooptation promotes consensus among firms on pursuing strategic sustainability goals (Crick & Crick, 2022; Dahmann & Roehrich, 2019). This is because sharing experiences through cooptation leads to the emergence and prevalence of accepted social norms that govern behaviour (Sarrica et al., 2016). For example, understanding the consequences of past generations' fishing practices enables Norwegian fishing firms to be more conscious of the importance of sustainable fishing practices (Johnsen et al., 2020). Accordingly, we argue that cooptation leads to increased sharing of sustainability-related information, which should increase sustainability awareness among participants. Therefore, we propose the following hypothesis:

H3. As firms engage in cooptation, their sustainability awareness will likely increase.

2.4. Sustainability awareness and firm's sustainability performance - H4

Sarkis (1995) proposed that firms run by managers or owners lacking sustainability awareness would suffer significant declines in profitability. This contention is credible because consumers are increasingly concerned with sustainability (Iyer & Kashyap, 2007; White et al., 2019). The change in consumers' sustainability awareness directly affects firms' market share and thus reduces their overall profitability (White et al., 2019). In this study, we argue that sustainability awareness should lead to increased awareness and concern about sustainability. Huijts, Molin, and Steg (2012) suggest that sustainability consciousness reduces the magnitude of the perceived risks and costs of adopting sustainability technologies. As such, firms led by managers or owners with strong sustainability consciousness are more inclined to integrate sustainability objectives into their business strategies (Roxas & Coetzer, 2012). Similarly, Schniederjans and Khalajhedayati (2020) argued that sustainability consciousness influences how firms anticipate the consequences of their actions and operations. As such, we argue that firms' awareness leads to sustainability consciousness and concern, which, in turn, should lead to the implementation of various sustainable practices and, subsequently, increase sustainability performance. Thus, we propose the following hypothesis:

H4. There is a positive association between an increase in firms' sustainability awareness and an improvement in their sustainability performance.

In sum, we proposed four hypotheses, representing the link between cooptation and firms' sustainability performance, mediated by dynamic capabilities and sustainability awareness (cf. Fig. 1). Next, we present the methods implemented to test these hypotheses.

3. Methods

3.1. Exploring the empirical context

Dolnicar et al. (2015) suggested that researchers conducting quantitative studies must adequately understand their research contexts to allow them to generate insights that have meaningful implications for practice. In addition, understanding the context helps reduce measurement errors, as it increases the relevance of the measurement indicators (Dana & Dana, 2005). Thus, as highlighted in the introduction, this study began with qualitative analysis. Specifically, we conducted semi-structured interviews with representatives of six actors in the Norwegian fishing industry to understand the research context and explore its dynamics. The interviewees were purposively sampled based on the following criteria: (a) firms that compete and cooperate simultaneously within the same industry and market, (b) firms that are part of the same cooperative network, and (c) evidence of ongoing cooperative activities at both ends of their supply chains, both upstream and downstream (Tashakkori et al., 2020). Consistent with Sogn-Grundvåg et al. (2021), the interviews confirmed the presence of coopetition activities in the Norwegian fishing industry, justifying it as a relevant case for testing the hypotheses developed in this study.

Different fishing associations have been formed in Norway based on geographic location. Our analysis of the interview data indicates that in this industry, coopetition is closely associated with the development of capabilities, such as knowledge enhancement, organisational responsiveness, and reflexive control. For instance, competing firms engage in regular meetings and joint programs to address customer needs and bridge knowledge gaps. Moreover, industry actors collaborate to identify and select suppliers capable of constructing boats with reduced fuel or oil consumption to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions. Additionally, coopetition plays a role in facilitating changes in outdated business practices during times of crisis, enabling actors to meet new customer demands. An example of this was observed during the COVID-19 pandemic when industry actors supported each other in reshaping their supply chains and finding alternative product distribution channels. Overall, the qualitative study indicated the significance of dynamic capabilities and sustainability awareness as mediating variables that connect coopetition to sustainability performance. For additional information on the preliminary qualitative study details and supporting quotes, please refer to Appendix 1.

Fig. 2 illustrates the implementation of coopetition practices within the Norwegian fishing supply chain, in which competing firms engage in collaborative efforts in specific domains while maintaining a competitive stance. Upstream of the chain, fishing companies compete for fish catches while cooperating in areas such as developing product quality standards, sharing information and communication technology solutions, and engaging in joint sustainability initiatives pertaining to fishing for litter. On the downstream side, they collaborate to sell first-hand sales through a shared sales organisation categorised by geographical location. However, they continue to compete in non-first-hand sales through their respective sales agents and marketing their catch in the same market.

3.2. Research design

Following this qualitative study, we developed a questionnaire to gather data from various industry actors to test our hypotheses. Using the key informant approach (Bouncken et al., 2018; Krause et al., 2018), the relevant informants for our study were owners, CEOs, or senior managers from whitefish producers across Norway. We targeted informants holding these positions for two reasons. First, based on the interviews with industry representatives, we concluded that matters related to coopetition are considered strategic; therefore, CEOs, directors, and senior managers are in a much better position to answer such issues. Second, as sustainable practices require significant commitment and investments (Fernandez et al., 2021; Munten et al., 2021), the final decision and willingness to optimise sustainability outcomes rest with the owners and top managers. Overall, we consider that CEOs, directors, and senior managers are the most knowledgeable and qualified to answer questions related to our focal constructs.

3.3. Operationalisation of variables

The questionnaire used in this study included questions that captured the focal variables of our hypotheses. The measurement items for these variables were initially sourced from prior research and subsequently modified to fit the context based on insights gained from in-depth interviews with industry representatives. Measurement items for all focal constructs were measured on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from ‘strongly disagree’ (1) to ‘strongly agree’ (7). The constructs were operationalised as follows.

Fig. 2. Coopetition activities in the Norwegian fishing industry.

Firms' sustainability performance (FSP) is the dependent variable in our model and was operationalised by three pillars of sustainability, namely, economic (FSP_E), social (FSP_S), and environmental (FSP_G). FSP_S was measured using three indicators, whereas FSP_E and FSP_G were measured using four indicators each. The indicators were based on previous studies (e.g. Crick & Crick, 2021; Guo et al., 2014; Kallmuenzer et al., 2021; Kumar et al., 2018; Paulraj et al., 2014). Regarding the measurement model, choosing a reflective or formative model is context-dependent (Khan et al., 2016). Some studies consider economic, social, and environmental sustainability to be independent (Kumar et al., 2018; Kumar & Rahman, 2016), indicating that they are not interchangeable and, thus, should be measured formatively (Malesios et al., 2020). However, other studies see these three pillars as independent yet interrelated elements sharing a common theme (Carmine & De Marchi, 2022; Hussain et al., 2016; Morawicki, 2012); therefore, they should be considered a reflection of sustainability (Kamble et al., 2020). From the interviews and extant literature, it was clear that the three pillars of sustainability in the fishing industry were interrelated. For instance, the long-term financial survival of a firm in the fishing industry depends primarily on not endangering the fish species and corals in the oceans and protecting society at large (Lindland et al., 2019). Therefore, this study considers FSP as a second-order construct reflected by the economic (FSC_E), environmental (FSC_G), and social (FSC_S) dimensions.

Coopetition (COOP) was the antecedent variable in our conceptual model. The operationalisation of coopetition in previous studies is inconclusive because it is operationalised in different ways (e.g. dummy variables, single-item proxies, and survey-based measures). However, this study used survey-based measures borrowed from previous studies (e.g. Bouncken et al., 2018; Crick & Crick, 2021; Paulraj et al., 2014) and modified them based on insights from semi-structured interviews. Eventually, five indicators were used to operationalise coopetition.

Dynamic Capabilities (DCs) are a mediating variable in our conceptual model. In line with the extant literature [e.g. Alinaghian et al., 2020; Teece, 2007], dynamic capabilities are operationalised as a higher-order construct reflected by three first-order components: (1) knowledge development (KND), (2) Organisational responsiveness (ORGR), and (3) reflexive control (REFC). Consistent with Beske et al. (2014), we define knowledge development as firms' routines related to assessing current and acquiring new industry-related knowledge to identify emerging threats in optimising sustainability goals. Similarly, operational responsiveness is defined as a firm's ability to respond to unforeseen changes to seize opportunities and address threats in the business environment (Aslam et al., 2018; Gruchmann et al., 2019; Mishra et al., 2022). Reflexive control enables actors to continuously assess ongoing sustainability requirements and conditions to maintain business functionality (Siems et al., 2021). Consistent with previous studies (Beske et al., 2014; Jiao et al., 2013; Kumar et al., 2018; Lin & Lei-Yu, 2014; Sancha et al., 2016) and considering the context of this study, we operationalised each first-order construct using three reflective indicators.

Sustainability awareness (SAW) was the second mediating variable in our conceptual model. This construct was measured using a single item. There has been debate among scholars on the use of single items for the measurement of constructs. However, based on their analysis, Bergkvist and Rossiter (2009) and Bergkvist (2015, 2016) recommend using a single item when measuring a concrete singular object and a concrete attribute. Similarly, Freed (2013) advocated using single-item measures for sufficiently narrow and unambiguous constructs. Based on the interviews conducted before the survey, it was apparent that 'sustainability' had become a household word among actors in the Norwegian fishing industry. As such, we considered sustainability awareness to be a concrete aspect. Therefore, we measured it using a 'global' single-item question that gauged the management's awareness of sustainability issues related to their supply chains.

Control variables. This study introduced firm size (FSIZE) and

industry experience (INDUE) as control variables. We included firm size because previous studies have argued that it is associated with overall profitability and investment in greener production practices (Bouncken et al., 2018; Pekovic et al., 2020). We measured this by the number of permanent and temporary employees. We include industry experience because it is well documented in the extant literature that firms' market share and profitability increase with industry experience. Thus, we assume that experienced firms might have more resources to engage in sustainability practices and increase their sustainability performance. We measured experience as the number of years a firm had been in business (Crick & Crick, 2021; Westhead et al., 2001). Table 1 presents the indicators used to measure the focal and control variables.

Table 1
Operationalisation of variables.

Variable	Indicators
Coopetition (COOP)	COOP1: We collaborate with our competitors to achieve our common sustainability goals COOP2: Active collaboration with our competitors is important for our sustainability efforts COOP3: We pursue the same sustainability goals as our competitors COOP4: We collaborate with our competitors to market our products COOP5: We work together with our competitors in standardising product quality
Knowledge development (KND)	KND1: We frequently conduct internal training KND2: We gain an advantage by combining our business knowledge with our partners' knowledge KND3: We frequently communicate with key business partners
Organisational responsiveness (ORGR)	ORGR1: We rapidly respond to market changes ORGR2: We strongly encourage innovative behaviour ORGR3: We frequently adjust our processes to capitalise on new opportunities
Reflexive control (REFC)	REFC1: We have quality control mechanisms across the country REFC2: We put sustainability labels on our products REFC3: We have well-functioning food tracking systems with our strategic partners
Sustainability awareness (SAW)	SAW: We are highly aware of sustainability issues in our supply chain.
Firm's economic performance (FSP_E)	FSP_E1: Our market share has improved in recent years FSP_E2: Our sales revenues have improved in recent years FSP_E3: Our cost-effectiveness has improved in recent years FSP_E4: Our overall profitability has improved in recent years
Firm's social performance (FSP_S)	FSP_S1: The participation of our company in local community development has improved in recent years FSP_S2: Our company contribution to community health and safety has improved in recent years FSP_S3: Improving the general welfare of stakeholders FSP_G1: Our company's reduction in emissions has increased in recent years FSP_G2: Our material reuse and recycling has increased in recent years
Firm's environmental performance (FSP_G)	FSP_G3: Our company has improved in terms of marine litter/waste reduction FSP_G4: Our company has improved in terms of energy saved due to conservation and efficiency measures
Firm size (FSIZE)	FSIZE: Categorical variable measured by the number of employees (Below 50 employees; between 50 and 500; above 500)
Industry experience (INDUE)	INDUE: categorical variable measured by the number of years the firm has been in business (less than seven years; more than seven years)

3.4. Data collection

Two practitioners pre-screened the questionnaire to determine whether the questions were relevant and clear (Podsakoff et al., 2012). Their feedback and input were then incorporated into the final version of the questionnaire. Subsequently, a list of Norwegian fishing firms was drawn from the Norwegian Seafood Council. The list contains 297 firms. Since the population size was rather small, we sent the questionnaire to all participants. The questionnaire was prepared and distributed using Nettskjema, a tool for designing and conducting online surveys developed and operated by the University of Oslo. In addition to having the most common features for creating and managing online surveys, we preferred Nettskjema because it is specifically designed to meet Norwegian privacy requirements. Data were collected from January to March 2022. To increase the response rate, three waves of emails were sent two weeks apart. Eventually, 97 usable responses were received, representing a response rate of 32.7%. This response rate is close to the reported average email survey response rate, which is approximately 30% (Lindemann, 2021).

In the past, researchers used rules of thumb, such as having a minimum sample size of 200 (Kline, 2011) or one that is greater than ten times the maximum number of inner or outer model links pointing at any latent variable in the model (Hair et al., 2011). However, more rigorous methods have been developed to determine an adequate sample size. Following Hair Jr et al. (2022), we applied the inverse square root method (Kock & Hadaya, 2018) to determine a sufficient sample size to attain 80% statistical power. Based on the initial analysis of the first 50 responses, the minimum path coefficient was 0.256, indicating that at least 94 observations were required to avoid a type 2 error. As such, the sample of 97 observations used in our final analysis is adequate. Among the respondents, 69 firms had fewer than 50 employees, 22 had between 50 and 500 employees, and only six had >500 employees. This distribution is consistent with the insights obtained from the interviews and previous studies (e.g. Sogn-Grundvåg et al., 2021), which indicate that small and medium-sized firms mainly dominate the Norwegian fishing industry. Therefore, it is reasonable to conclude that the sample used in this study was representative.

3.5. Assessing non-response bias and common method variance

We conducted a paired-sample test to compare the responses of the first and last 25% of the respondents (24 each). No significant difference was found between the two groups ($p > 0.05$), suggesting that the study did not suffer from non-response bias (Table 2). The assessment of potential common method bias in survey studies should not be ignored, especially when data are collected from a single respondent per firm (Cao & Zhang, 2011; Podsakoff et al., 2003). Clear and concise surveys can help reduce the risk of common method bias (Podsakoff et al., 2012; Siemsen et al., 2010). With this in mind, the survey took approximately seven to ten minutes to complete and was worded in clear and understandable language to avoid ambiguity in questions and minimise respondent fatigue. Additionally, the analysis of Harman's single-factor test conducted on the dataset revealed that a single factor explained only

Table 2
Assessing non-response bias by paired sample *t*-test of the latent variables.

Variables	Mean scores of the first 24 responses	Mean scores of the last 24 responses	P(T ≤ t) two-tail
COOP	4.757	4.403	0.432
REFC	5.875	5.479	0.151
SAW	5.958	6.049	0.675
KND	5.750	5.802	0.837
CONSC	5.833	5.917	0.799
FSP-G	4.813	4.823	0.975
FSP-S	5.567	5.400	0.603
FSP-E	5.146	5.333	0.598

21.17% of the total variance, below the conservative threshold of 50% (Podsakoff et al., 2003). The item loadings for the factors were also significant, so it can be concluded that common method bias was not a problem in this study.

4. Analysis

The analysis in this study was conducted using partial least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM), followed by necessary condition analysis (NCA). PLS-SEM was selected for three reasons. First, our model includes higher-order constructs, which can be analysed more effectively using PLS-SEM (Hair et al., 2013; Henseler et al., 2009; Richter et al., 2016; Sarstedt et al., 2020). Second, our model includes mediation effects, and according to Sarstedt et al. (2020), such models should be analysed using composite-based SEM methods such as PLS-SEM to overcome the limitations of both regression- and factor-based SEM analyses. The analysis deployed SmartPLS 3 version 3.7 (Ringle et al., 2015), the leading PLS-SEM software. Third, Hair et al. (2019) suggest that PLS-SEM should be applied when a study requires latent variable scores for follow-up analyses, such as the NCA conducted in this study.

4.1. Measurement model assessment

This study's model consists of two higher-order constructs (HOCs): dynamic capabilities (DCs) and firms' sustainability performance (FSP). Since all HOCs and their corresponding lower-order constructs (LOCs) are measured reflectively, a reflective-reflective model is applied using the repeated indicators approach (Becker et al., 2012). That is, all items of the reflective LOCs are simultaneously assigned to the reflective measurement model of the HOC (Hair Jr et al., 2017; Lohmöller, 1989). The measurement model was assessed for internal consistency reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity.

4.1.1. Reliability and convergent validity of LOCs

Internal consistency reliability was assessed using a novel and more effective measure (ρ_A) instead of the traditional Cronbach's alpha (Henseler et al., 2014). To establish reliability and convergent validity, the loading of ρ_A values and average variance extracted (AVE) should be higher than 0.7 and 0.5, respectively (Hair Jr et al., 2022). In addition, the indicator loadings should be at least 0.7. The reliability and convergent validity results for LOCs are presented in Table 3, along with the items' factor loadings. We find support for the LOCs because all values of ρ_A and AVE are within the recommended thresholds (Sarstedt et al., 2019). As for indicator loadings, all meet the recommended thresholds except COOP5 (0.635), KND3 (0.681), and REFC2 (0.698). Hair Jr et al. (2022) suggest that researchers can retain indicators with lower loadings to ensure content validity of the construct as long as they are between 0.4 and 0.7, and their inclusion does not lower internal consistency reliability and convergent validity below the recommended thresholds. Therefore, we retained these indicators.

4.1.2. Discriminant validity of LOCs

Discriminant validity assesses whether a model's individual constructs are empirically distinguishable. We used the heterotrait-monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT) to check discriminant validity, as recommended by Hair Jr et al. (2022). The recommended threshold for establishing it is that HTMT ratio values should be below 0.85 for conceptually different constructs and 0.90 for conceptually similar constructs (Hair Jr et al., 2022). The discriminant validity of the constructs in this study was established because all HTMT values were below the recommended thresholds (see Table 4).

4.1.3. Assessing internal consistency reliability of HOCs

We followed established guidelines for assessing the reliability and validity of HOCs (Hair Jr et al., 2017; Henseler et al., 2015; Sarstedt

Table 3
Loadings, reliability, and validity for LOCs.

Indicator	Mean	Std. dev	Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite reliability	AVE
SAW	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
COOP1	4.427	1.836	0.897	0.857	0.914	0.895	0.633
COOP2	4.646	1.762	0.869				
COOP3	4.802	1.699	0.818				
COOP4	3.802	1.993	0.730				
COOP5	4.438	1.957	0.635				
FSP-E1	4.876	1.372	0.881	0.924	0.926	0.946	0.814
FSP-E2	5.010	1.640	0.924				
FSP-E3	4.979	1.450	0.907				
FSP-E4	5.062	1.498	0.897				
FSP-G1	4.646	1.472	0.812	0.865	0.866	0.908	0.712
FSP-G2	4.897	1.509	0.865				
FSP-G3	5.474	1.458	0.846				
FSP-G4	4.979	1.464	0.853				
FSP-S1	4.567	1.267	0.825	0.873	0.883	0.923	0.800
FSP-S2	4.485	1.202	0.931				
FSP-S3	4.423	1.275	0.924				
KND1	5.042	1.620	0.769	0.594	0.604	0.785	0.549
KND2	5.722	1.290	0.769				
KND3	6.464	0.850	0.681				
REFC1	4.371	1.852	0.821	0.682	0.705	0.823	0.609
REFC2	4.979	1.844	0.698				
REFC3	6.134	1.433	0.815				
ORGR1	6.031	1.177	0.755	0.720	0.727	0.843	0.641
ORGR2	5.835	1.274	0.819				
ORGR3	5.794	1.292	0.827				

Table 4
HTMT ratios for LOCs.

	COOP	FSP-E	FSP-G	FSP-S	KND	REFC	ORGR
COOP							
FSP-E	0.255						
FSP-G	0.309	0.551					
FSP-S	0.445	0.610	0.629				
KND	0.527	0.240	0.388	0.415			
REFC	0.552	0.346	0.599	0.631	0.598		
ORGR	0.177	0.407	0.578	0.593	0.526	0.489	

et al., 2019). Thus, the assessment of the reliability and validity of HOCs is based on their LOCs, which are interpreted as indicators of HOCs. In other words, the path coefficients between the LOCs and HOCs are used as indicator loadings, and the average correlations between the constructs are used to calculate AVE, Cronbach's alpha, and composite reliability (see Appendix 2).

AVE was calculated using the mean of the squared loadings of the higher-order construct for the relationships between LOCs and HOCs (Hair Jr et al., 2017). Using Eq. (1) in Appendix 2, the AVE is 0.584 and 0.686 for dynamic capabilities and firms' sustainability performance, respectively. Both AVE values were above the conservative threshold, indicating convergent validity. (Becker et al., 2012; Hair et al., 2017; Henseler et al., 2009). The composite reliabilities for dynamic capabilities and firms' sustainability performance are 0.808 and 0.867, respectively. Similarly, Cronbach's alpha for dynamic capabilities and firms' sustainability performance are 0.644 and 0.772, respectively. Overall, the composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha values show that both HOCs meet the recommended internal consistency reliability as their values are well above the conservative threshold of 0.6 for higher-order constructs (Hair et al., 2018; Sarstedt et al., 2019).

4.2. Structural model estimation

We analysed the structural model by bootstrapping using 10,000 subsamples. The assessment criteria include the sign, magnitude, and significance of the inner path coefficients. Thus, we checked the coefficient of determination (R^2), effect size (f^2), and internal predictive

relevance (Q^2) (Hair et al., 2018; Henseler et al., 2009). We began by estimating the direct impact of competition on firms' sustainability performance without considering the mediating variables. This test aims to validate the widely advocated assumption that competition is crucial for increasing firms' sustainability performance (Chauhan et al., 2022; Dania et al., 2018; Koberg & Longoni, 2019; Seuring et al., 2022). The findings depicted in Fig. 3 and Table 5 support this assumption, as the direct impact of competition on firms' sustainability performance is positive (0.373) and statistically significant ($p = 0.000$). The model does not suffer from multicollinearity, as the variance inflation factor (VIF) values are <3 (Hair Jr et al., 2022). However, the two control variables, firm size and industry experience, do not significantly affect firms' sustainability performance.

With the direct effect of competition on firms' sustainability performance established, our analysis shifted its attention to the main objective of testing the hypotheses regarding the mechanism that links competition to firms' sustainability performance. To achieve this, we tested the conceptual model developed in this study (see Fig. 1). The results are illustrated in Fig. 4 and Table 6. As reported in Table 6, this model also does not suffer from multicollinearity, as the VIF values are <3 . The path coefficients ranged from 0.104 to 0.426, while the effect sizes (f^2) of the direct paths ranged from 0.118 to 0.222. These effect sizes indicate that the direct paths have small to moderate magnitudes (Hair Jr et al., 2022). However, including the two mediating variables led to an R^2 value of 0.434, representing a substantial increase compared to the R^2 value of 0.171 obtained in the model without mediating variables (Fig. 3). Finally, the Q^2 value is greater than zero, indicating that the model has internal predictive relevance.

The results demonstrate that H1, which proposes that firms that engage in competition are likely to increase their dynamic capabilities, is supported, as the corresponding path coefficient is positive (0.426) and significant ($p = 0.000$). H2 suggests that dynamic capabilities positively affect firms' sustainability performance. This hypothesis is supported, as the corresponding path coefficient is positive (0.357) and significant ($p = 0.000$). H3 suggests that competition is positively related to sustainability awareness. The results demonstrate that the corresponding path coefficient is positive (0.366) and significant ($p = 0.000$), thus providing support. Finally, H4 posits that sustainability awareness is positively related to firms' sustainability performance. This hypothesis was

Fig. 3. Structural model estimation without the proposed mediational mechanism.

Table 5
Structural model estimation results.

Direct paths	Coefficient	f ²	VIF	p-value
COOP- > FSP	0.373	0.163	1.032	0.000 ^a
FIRMS- > FSP	-0.026	0.001	1.082	0.792 ⁿ
INDUE- > FSP	0.144	0.023	1.075	0.062 ⁿ
R ² _{FSP}	0.171			
Adj. R ² _{FSP}	0.145			
Q ² _{FSP}	0.081			

Notes: ^asignificant at $p \leq 0.01$; ⁿ not significant.

supported because the corresponding inner path coefficient was positive (0.318) and significant ($p = 0.002$). A notable observation is that the direct effect of cooperation becomes insignificant following the inclusion of the two mediating variables, indicating that dynamic capabilities and sustainability awareness fully mediate the relationship between cooperation and firms' sustainability performance. The two control variables do not appear to significantly affect sustainability performance. Although the coefficient of the size of the cooperating firms (FSIZE) is positive (0.016), its impact on sustainability is not significant ($p = 0.897$). Similarly, industry experience (INDUE) has a positive coefficient (0.096), but its effect on FSP is not significant ($p = 0.136$).

4.3. Mediation analysis

We performed a mediation analysis to assess the nature of the mediating role of dynamic capabilities and sustainability awareness. Thus, we evaluated the direct and indirect effects of cooperation on sustainability performance. According to Hair Jr et al. (2022), indirect effects must be interpreted based on the values of bootstrapped confidence intervals. Table 7 presents the results. The analysis revealed that

the indirect effect of cooperation on sustainability performance through dynamic capabilities was significant ($\beta = 0.150$ [0.065, 0.273], $p \leq 0.01$), as was the indirect effect through awareness ($\beta = 0.116$ [0.031, 0.236], $p \leq 0.05$). Furthermore, the overall indirect effect was significant ($\beta = 0.378$, $p \leq 0.01$). As we found that the direct effect of cooperation on sustainability performance disappeared following the inclusion of the two mediating variables (cf. Table 6), the structural model exhibits an indirect-only mediation effect (Hair Jr et al., 2022). Had we found a positive and significant direct effect of cooperation after including the mediating variables, the model would exhibit complementary mediation.

4.4. Necessary condition analysis

Following Bokrantz and Dul (2022), who advocate building robust supply chain management theories through necessary condition analysis, we examined whether DCs and SAW are prerequisites for optimising FSP. The analysis was conducted according to the guidelines of Richter et al. (2020), Dul et al. (2020), and Dul (2021). Thus, we used latent variable scores generated by PLS-SEM (Richter et al., 2020), importing them into the R software where analysis was conducted using NCA R package version 3.1.1 (Dul, 2021). The NCA results are illustrated in Fig. 5 and Table 8. In line with the recommended guidelines (Dul, 2019; Dul, 2021; Dul et al., 2020; Richter et al., 2020), the results were assessed based on the effect sizes (d), p-values, and bottlenecks for each independent variable.

The NCA results demonstrate that the effect sizes (d) for both dynamic capabilities (DCs) and sustainability awareness (SAW) are above the conservative threshold ($d \leq 0.1$) and significant ($p \leq 0.01$), indicating that the two variables are mandatory for sustainability performance. The effects of dynamic capabilities (0.276) and sustainability

Fig. 4. Structural model estimation, including the proposed mediational mechanism.

Table 6
Structural model estimation results.

Paths	Coefficients	f ²	VIF	p-value
COOP- > FSP	0.104	0.015	1.274	0.287 ⁿ
H1: COOP- > DCs	0.426	0.222	1.000	0.000 ^a
H2: DCs- > FSP	0.357	0.143	1.674	0.000 ^a
H3: COOP- > SAW	0.366	0.155	1.000	0.000 ^a
H4: SAW- > FSP	0.318	0.122	1.515	0.002 ^a
FIRMS- > FSP	0.016	0.000	1.170	0.897 ⁿ
INDUE- > FSP	0.096	0.015	1.099	0.136 ⁿ
R ² _{FSP}	0.434			
Adj. R ² _{FSP}	0.403			
Q ² _{FSP}	0.207			

Notes: ^asignificant at p ≤ 0.01; ⁿ not significant.

Table 7
Assessment of the indirect effects.

Indirect paths	Coefficient	SD	t-value	P value	BI [2.5%, 97.5%]
COOP- > DCs - > FSC-SP	0,150	0,053	2844	0.004 ^a	[0.065, 0.273]
COOP- > SAW- > FSC-SP	0,116	0,052	2218	0.013 ^b	[0.031, 0.236]

Notes: ^asignificant at p ≤ 0.01; ^bsignificant at p ≤ 0.05.

awareness (0.313) on firms' sustainability performance (FSP) are moderate and large, respectively (Dul et al., 2020). The necessary conditions were further evaluated in terms of bottlenecks. The results show that

two necessary conditions must be present to achieve 50% sustainability performance. Dynamic capabilities must be at least 8.5%, and sustainability awareness must be at least 1.8%. However, the results showed that increasing sustainability awareness beyond 85.2% did not further increase sustainability performance.

5. Discussion

Cooperation is one of the potential keys to improving sustainability performance (Koberg & Longoni, 2019; Seuring et al., 2022). Even in the broader context of sustainable development, Manzhynski and Figge (2020) suggest that cooperation is required. Although these assertions are appealing, there is limited empirical evidence to support them. Besides, there is a crucial question about how cooperation increases a firm's sustainability performance. This study proposes a conceptual framework with dynamic capabilities and sustainability awareness as the underlying mechanism linking cooperation to firms' sustainability performance. The results show that firms that pursue cooperation tend to have higher levels of dynamic capabilities, which in turn are related to higher levels of sustainability performance. They also showed that cooperation is significantly associated with increased sustainability awareness, which in turn is connected to higher levels of sustainability performance. The direct effect of cooperation on sustainability performance became insignificant after introducing the mediating variables, which, according to Zhao et al. (2010), signifies that no other potential mediating factors play a meaningful role in our research context. Finally, we found that dynamic capabilities (DCs) and sustainability awareness are necessary to increase sustainability performance. As discussed below, these findings provide valuable insights for advancing theory, practice,

Fig. 5. NCA plots.

Table 8
The bottleneck analysis.

FSP	Effect size	Bottleneck										
		0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
DCs	0.276***	NN	NN	NN	NN	NN	8.5	25.2	41.8	58.5	75.1	91.7
SAW	0.313***	NN	NN	NN	NN	NN	1.8	22.6	43.5	64.3	85.2	NA

Notes: The effect size is based on ceiling envelopment-free disposal hull ceiling (CE-FDH). Significance testing was performed using 10,000 permutations (***) significant at $p < 0.01$.

and policy.

5.1. Theoretical contribution

The results of this study contribute to the theory in three ways. First, our study provides empirical evidence regarding the effect of coopetition on sustainability performance. In recent years, scholars have increasingly explored the drivers of sustainable performance (e.g. Bourlakis et al., 2014; Iqbal et al., 2020; Li, 2022) to develop a theory to guide actors in promoting sustainable performance. While recent studies have investigated the outcomes of coopetition (e.g. economic performance, innovation, and organisational learning), little attention has been paid to its role in achieving firms' sustainability performance (Mirzabeiki et al., 2022). Our findings demonstrate that coopetition can lead to increased sustainability performance across social, environmental, and economic dimensions.

Second, responding to Gnyawali and Charleton (2018) call to investigate how coopetition influences its outcomes, this study proposed and tested a conceptual model including dynamic capabilities and sustainability awareness as mediating variables. Mirzabeiki et al. (2022) suggest that coopetition affects sustainability performance by reducing logistics costs and carbon footprint, bolstering the competitiveness of the regional economy, and mitigating emissions. We contend that these factors do not constitute a mechanism through which coopetition influences sustainability. Instead, they represent distinct elements of sustainability performance that can be affected by coopetition. Our study contributes to the advancement of coopetition theory by providing valuable insights into the mechanisms governing the relationship between coopetition and sustainability performance. Our findings indicate that coopetition improves sustainability performance through relevant

dynamic capabilities such as knowledge development, organisational responsiveness, reflexive control, and fostering sustainability awareness.

Third, the generated insights into the role of dynamic capabilities and sustainability awareness as prerequisites for sustainability performance are crucial for advancing theory. As noted by Bokrantz and Dul (2022), a theory that does not incorporate specific necessary conditions fails to adequately predict an outcome. Necessity theories are powerful because they predict the absence of an outcome variable when a single causal factor (i.e. the necessary condition) is absent. In other words, necessary conditions do not guarantee the occurrence of an outcome but ensure its non-occurrence if the necessary conditions are absent (Dul, 2016). Prior research suggests that dynamic capabilities are a requisite for enhancing sustainability performance in firms (Gold et al., 2010; Kumar et al., 2018). However, no empirical evidence has substantiated these claims. Our study contributes to building a theory on the determinants of firms' sustainability performance by identifying the factors required to ensure its actualisation. Thus, our findings establish that dynamic capabilities and sustainability awareness constitute the causal mechanism underlying the relationship between coopetition and enhanced sustainability performance in firms and reveal that these factors are indispensable for achieving such enhancement. As a result, this study helps delineate the generalisable and applicable domain of interventions aimed at boosting sustainability performance by illustrating the essential prerequisites for such enhancement.

5.2. Managerial and policy implications

The findings of this study offer a basis for actionable managerial and policy recommendations. First, it highlights that coopetition can serve as

a valuable means of fostering dynamic capabilities and enhancing sustainability awareness, particularly for small and medium-sized firms. Through coopetition, such firms can amplify their understanding of sustainability issues and consolidate their efforts and resources to cultivate their dynamic capabilities. Thus, we strongly advocate that owners and managers of small- and medium-sized firms that have not yet adopted a coopetition strategy or those that do not actively practice it should embrace and increase their engagement. Importantly, coopetition should focus on increasing awareness of sustainability and building capabilities such as technological solutions, responsiveness, and knowledge development. To this end, coopetition actors should collaborate and share resources to increase resource utilisation efficiency. Likewise, member firms should collectively explore innovative solutions and adopt sustainable technologies to enhance their environmental performance.

Second, although this study revealed that coopetition positively impacts firms' sustainability performance by increasing their dynamic capabilities and sustainability awareness, it is crucial to note that these factors can also arise from other sources. Hence, we argue that, in addition to coopetition, managers should consider implementing other interventions that foster dynamic capabilities and sustainability awareness. For example, [Chen and Lee \(2009\)](#) suggest that firms can develop dynamic capabilities by engaging in repetitive practices and learning from their own experiences, codifying such experiences, and promoting their managers' ability to integrate and recombine knowledge to create new valuable competencies. Similarly, providing education and training programs to employees and management can augment awareness of sustainability issues and encourage sustainable practices ([Saeed et al., 2019](#)). Such internal programs could include training on topics such as energy efficiency, circular economy, waste reduction, and sustainable sourcing.

Third, we recommend that policymakers aspiring to enhance sustainability performance should strongly consider the promotion of coopetition among industry actors. Our findings demonstrate the positive impact of coopetition on firms' sustainability performance through the development of dynamic capabilities and sustainability awareness. However, implementing coopetition poses various challenges, including additional financial and time costs, loss of control, opportunism, and profit-sharing problems ([Morris et al., 2007](#)). Policymakers can offer financial incentives, such as grants or subsidies, to encourage firms to engage in coopetition. These incentives can help offset the costs associated with collaboration and encourage firms to explore opportunities for cooperation. Considering the significant role of sustainability awareness and dynamic capabilities, joint activities should focus on enhancing these two aspects. For instance, policymakers can create platforms or networks that facilitate knowledge-sharing and collaboration among firms. These platforms allow firms to exchange information, best practices, and resources, fostering a cooperative environment.

Policymakers can also establish regulations and policies that simultaneously encourage collaboration and competition, for example, by developing legal frameworks that enable firms to engage in cooperative activities without violating antitrust laws. In addition, they can support industry-specific initiatives that promote coopetition. This can involve funding R&D projects focused on collaborative innovation, sustainability, or resource sharing within a particular industry. Equally important is that they encourage firms to form strategic partnerships and alliances by highlighting the benefits of coopetition. This can be achieved through awareness campaigns, case studies, and success stories that highlight the positive outcomes of collaborative efforts. In sum, policymakers can create an enabling environment that supports and promotes coopetition among firms by implementing these measures, fostering collaboration,

and enhancing overall competitiveness and sustainability.

6. Closing remarks

This study examined dynamic capabilities and sustainability awareness as the underlying mechanisms in the relationship between coopetition and firms' sustainability performance, drawing on the Norwegian fishing industry as a research context. This industry was deemed appropriate because of its rapidly changing business environment, characterised by fluctuating consumer preferences, evolving technologies, and changing laws and regulations. The study developed and tested four hypotheses, and the results confirmed that dynamic capabilities and sustainability awareness mediate coopetition and firms' sustainability performance. Furthermore, we found that dynamic capabilities and sustainability awareness are mandatory for increasing firms' sustainability performance.

Although our study contributes to the literature on the relationship between coopetition and sustainability performance, it is important to acknowledge its limitations. As a result, we identified several potential avenues for future research that warrant exploration. First, the analysis was based on cross-sectional data, making it challenging to uncover changes over time. Future studies could conduct longitudinal research to explore the evolution of coopetition among actors. Second, this study did not consider the potential moderating effect of environmental dynamism on the relationship between dynamic capabilities and sustainability performance. Thus, future studies can examine the contingent role of business environment dynamism.

Third, the analysis was based on only one industry in one country, making it challenging to generalise the findings to other food industries. Thus, future studies could replicate this study in different contexts. Additionally, since the study only focused on coopetition as a driver of dynamic capabilities and sustainability awareness, future studies may empirically explore other sources of dynamic capabilities and sustainability awareness in fishing and other food industries. Finally, the study provides empirical evidence that lower-order capabilities, such as knowledge development, organisational responsiveness, and reflexive control, help organisations develop dynamic capabilities. However, the development of dynamic capabilities is expensive. Future studies could examine the interaction among these lower-order capabilities to explore the importance and role of each in improving sustainability performance. This will provide managers with insights into which lower-order capabilities should be prioritised.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix 1. A preliminary qualitative investigation¹

	Primary data (Semi-structured interviews) ¹	
	Number of interviews	6
	Combined interview length	335 min
	Transcribed pages	61
Data collection	Cases	Case A; Case B; Case C; and Case D [All cases are fishing companies that belong to the Norwegian Frozen at Sea (NFAS) association]
	Interviewee code	Manager - Case A; Director - Case B; Manager – Case D (two interviews); Director – Case D, Director - NFAS
	Secondary Data (for data triangulation)	Both internal and external sources which include The Fisheries Act, sustainability reports, webpages, press releases, standard guidelines, and Marine Act
Analysis	Abductive reasoning	The analysis started with description exploration of the entire data (i.e., transcribed interviews) using qualitative software, NVivo 12 Pro. Focus was on the most frequent and meaningful words. Codes were developed and thereafter using abductive reasoning this helped the Authors to get initial understanding of the second- order codes. Finally, we used content analysis to develop themes by aggregating the second-order codes.
	Coopetition helped to generate dynamic capabilities (knowledge management, organisational responsiveness, and reflexive control) and sustainability awareness which in turn promote actors' sustainability performance.	
	Quotes	
	Coopetition contributing to knowledge development	<p>“...We invite our competitors and have a three-day program together...”(Director, Case D)</p> <p>“in this group, instead of each actor sitting on their own knowledge network, we try to combine the knowledge we have” (Manager, Case A).</p> <p>“...we try to say that instead of sitting on one island here in one island there, (..) we try to meet and going over the bridge and think together. (..) I think it's the knowledge that each part has, and we try to combine them to get better together...” (Manager, Case A)</p> <p>“... this helps us to promote, secure access to the market, and also be our information channel both media and information” (Director, NFAS)</p> <p>Quotes</p> <p>“...it's kind of a customer wants something produced in a specific way and our firm cannot meet this specific demand, then you need to reach to another vessel (coopetitor)....” (Manager, Case A)</p>
Findings	Coopetition contributing to organisational responsiveness	
	Coopetition contributing to reflexive control	<p>“...we see in some respects that we are able to change the way we work to face the crisis together and we share the knowledge to do that....” (Manager, Case D)</p> <p>Quotes</p> <p>“We have a shared system where we can go back from minute to minute and know where the boats have been and where they have been catching. And when they are putting out or shooting the line, as we call it or pulling it, we will know where it was when it was and all these details. So, all the fish we take onboard is traced, and then it's put on a label.” (Director, Case D)</p> <p>“...we have made or worked together to make standard guidelines of what you need to do on board to comply with sustainability requirement” (Manager, Case A)</p> <p>Quotes</p>
	Coopetition contributing to sustainability awareness	<p>“We are very (conscious) on sustainability for what we're doing, how we operate, how we operate our vessels, how we catch the fish. So, we talk a lot about sustainability in our business network”. (Manager, Case A).</p> <p>“...and that is why we say we fish for the future. And we take responsibility for harvesting in a way that will be good for the future generation. And you can say that this our focus in this group...” (Director, Case B).</p>

Appendix 2. Computation of reliability for higher-order constructs (HOCs)

AVE for HOCs

$$AVE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^M l_i^2}{M} \tag{1}$$

where, l_i and M represent loadings of the LOCs of specific HOCs and M LOCs ($i = 1, \dots, M$). The loadings are shown in Fig. 2. Using formula (1) above, the AVE for DCs is $0.584 (0.737^2 + 0.763^2 + 0.791^2)/3$. Similarly, the AVE for FSP is $0.686 (0.837^2 + 0.828^2 + 0.819^2)/3$.

Composite reliability (ρ_c) for HOCs

$$Composite\ reliability(\rho_c) = \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^M l_i)^2}{(\sum_{i=1}^M l_i)^2 + \sum_{i=1}^M var(e_i)} \tag{2}$$

Where e_i stands for measurement error of the low-order constructs (LOCs) i , and $var.(e_i)$ represents measurement error variance (computed as $1-l_i^2$).

¹ Harun et al. (2022) reports the study in detail.

Therefore, composite reliability of two HOCs are computed as follows:

$$DCs'(\rho_c) = \frac{(0.737 + 0.763 + 0.791)^2}{(0.737 + 0.763 + 0.791)^2 + (1 - 0.791)^2 (1 - 0.763)^2 + (1 - 0.737)^2} = 0.808$$

$$FSP's(\rho_c) = \frac{(0.837 + 0.828 + 0.819)^2}{(0.837 + 0.828 + 0.819)^2 + (1 - 0.837)^2 (1 - 0.828)^2 + (1 - 0.819)^2} = 0.867$$

Cronbach's Alpha for HOCs

$$Cronbach's\ Alpha = \frac{M \cdot \bar{r}}{1 + (M - 1) \cdot \bar{r}} \tag{3}$$

Here, \bar{r} represents mean correlation between LOCs. In this study the HOCs had three LOCs in each ($M = 3$), and average correlations between LOCs scores are 0.377 and 0.530 for DCs and FSP, respectively as shown below.

Correlations between LOCs of DCs and FSP

	KND	REFC	ORGR	FSP-E	FSP-G	FSP-S
KND	1			1		
REFC	0.399	1		0.496	1	
ORGR	0.362	0.369	1	0.547	0.548	1
Average	0.377			0.530		

Therefore:

$$DCs' Cronbach's\ Alpha = \frac{3 \times 0.377}{1 + (3 - 1) \cdot 0.377} = 0.644$$

$$FSP's Cronbach's\ Alpha = \frac{3 \times 0.530}{1 + (3 - 1) \cdot 0.530} = 0.772$$

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